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GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTIONS

HELEOPHRYNIDAE**Heleophryne depressa**

FitzSimons, 1946

Cederberg Ghost Frog

Range Extension and Lower Elevational Limit**O.L. ANGUS**

The Cederberg Ghost Frog (*Heleophryne depressa* FitzSimons, 1946) is a cryptic species, both in appearance and behaviour, with shy, rupicolous adults and tadpoles adapted to fast-flowing mountain streams (Du Preez & Channing 2017). The common name is misleading, as the species was neither described from nor is endemic to the Cederberg. Its range extends from Montagu in the south to the slopes below Krakadouw Peak in the north (Angus et al. 2025). Due to the strong morphological conservatism of larvae in the genus, species-level identification based on morphology alone is unreliable (Channing et al. 2012). Distribution is therefore commonly used to infer identity. The Klein-Berg River, which flows through Nuwekloof Pass, is assumed to separate *H. depressa* from its close relative *H. purcelli* Sclater, 1898, with mountains north of the river considered to harbour populations of *H. depressa* (Angus et al. 2025a, 2025b).

One such mountain is the Piketberg massif (Fig. 1), situated on the west coast of the southwestern Cape. The dominant vegetation type (*sensu* Mucina & Rutherford 2006) is Piketberg Sandstone Fynbos, a montane community characteristic of the range and other mountains

inhabited and other mountains inhabited by *Heleophryne* species. The massif is a prominent inselberg, rising abruptly from surrounding sandy and shale plains and reaching 1458 m at its summit (Sebrakop). The terrain is steep, with isolated peaks and plateaus. Given the massif's aridity, with mean annual rainfall between 320 and 860 mm, only a few perennial streams persist on the mountain. Piketberg supports a subset of the montane herpetofauna found on neighbouring ranges, including *Breviceps montanus* Power, 1926, *Breviceps gibbosus* Linnaeus, 1758, *Cordylus oelofseni* Mouton & van Wyk, 1990, and *Goggia hexapora* Branch, Bauer & Good, 1995 (Tolley et al. 2006). Several species expected to occur in such habitat, such as *Ouroborus cataphractus*, Boie, 1828, *Capensibufo tradouwi* Hewitt, 1926, and *Heleophryne depressa*, have not previously been recorded. To investigate the potential presence of the latter species, O. Angus and K. Brand surveyed a tributary of the Krom Antonies River on the west-facing slopes of Moutonshoek Valley on 20 January 2025.

At the first pool investigated, 'Jacuzzi Pool', near the old Scheppie Saus campsite (32° 44' 34.0" S 18° 44' 13.5" E; 178 m a.s.l.), multiple larvae of *H. depressa* were found grazing on and beneath submerged rocks, leaving feeding trails along the

Figure 1(Left) The Piketberg massif located on the west coast of the southwestern Cape, and (Right) the small tributary of the Krom Antonies Rivier that was surveyed (white dot), along with two other streams that appear to show suitable breeding habitat for *H. depressa* (red dots).

A

B

Figure 2lateral (A) and dorsal view (B) of a single *H. depressa* tadpole that was photographed and posted on iNaturalist by the author (Angus, 2025c).

Figure 3(A-D) Adult and larval habitat photographs along the course of the stream that was surveyed, only some pools contained tadpoles of *H. depressa*.

rock surfaces. They were identified to genus by their distinctive sucker mouths (Fig. 2), a trait unique to *Heleophryne* among South African frogs, and to species level based on the distributional criteria outlined above (Du Preez & Channing 2017). The survey extended approximately 800 m upstream, terminating at 32° 44' 33.3" S 18° 44' 40.2" E. The stream is perennial, with pools up to 1.5 m deep, interspersed with boulders and shaded by occasional trees that form a partial canopy (Fig. 3). Surface flow is discontinuous, with flowing sections separated by dry stretches underlain by subsurface flow, likely reconnected during winter rainfall. Terrestrial microhabitats such as overhangs, moss-covered rock faces, ferns and narrow crevices, all known to shelter adult *H. depressa*, were abundant (Fig. 3-C). These areas were searched thoroughly but no adults were found. Multiple cohorts of *H. depressa* larvae were observed, including individuals likely from the most recent breeding season. No tadpoles were found upstream of 32° 44' 34.9" S 18° 44' 26.8" E, despite the presence of suitable habitat, with observations confined to a 300 m stream segment. In contrast, tadpoles of *Amietia fuscigula* Duméril and Bibron, 1841, were widespread, even occupying stagnant pools typically unsuitable for *Heleophryne*. In other pools, *Heleophryne* were absent despite no obvious habitat features, such as reduced flow or siltation, that would make them unsuitable (Weeber et al. 2023), potentially indicating a small breeding population.

These observations establish a new lower elevational limit for the species at 178 m asl. The next lowest known record is from 270 m near Porterville, approximately 38 km away (see Fig. 1)

(Jjrepublic 2019). Given the extent of unsuitable lowland habitat and current climatic conditions, gene flow between the Piketberg population and other *H. depressa* populations is unlikely. The occurrence of *H. depressa* on Piketberg is not unexpected, given the climatic and topographical similarities it shares with the Cederberg. What is surprising, however, is that this population has continued to persist into contemporary times under ongoing habitat degradation on Piketberg. Most rivers on the mountain have been dammed at some point along their course to supply farms, which has disrupted natural stream flow and introduced pesticides and fertilisers into the water. Major perennial rivers, such as the Boesmans and both Platkloof Rivers (West and East), along with minor streams, are heavily invaded by alien plant species, rendering them unsuitable for *H. depressa*. The population is likely confined to the upper Krom Antonies Rivier and its tributaries in the Moutonshoek Valley, facing high extinction risk from small size, invasive plants, water abstraction, and climate change. Additionally, the lower pools where tadpoles were observed are lightly infested with *Phragmites* reeds, and are used for recreational swimming, which has led to increased sedimentation, displacement of submerged rocks, and accumulation of litter. This risk becomes more acute if the population proves to be evolutionarily distinct or represents a cryptic taxon. While it is unlikely that the species will occur outside the Moutonshoek Valley, photographs from Banghoek Nature Reserve (Fig. 4-B,C) suggest potential habitat that warrant investigation.

In conclusion, this survey extends both the western range limit and lower elevational boundary for *Heleophryne depressa*. More broadly, it reveals

Figure 4(A) Extensive seepages in the upper reaches of Moutonshoek Valley on Piketberg that could hold populations of *Capensibufo tradouwi* (Photo by Ralph Pina, 2020). Photographs found online of (B) a small stream in Banghoek Private Nature Reserve (Photo by Matt and Darren, 2023), and (C) the upper reaches of the Krom Antonies Rivier (Photo by Scheppie Saus, 2018), that appear to be suitable for *H. depressa* to breed in.

that Piketberg supports a more diverse montane herpetofauna than previously recorded. This is likely due to historical under-sampling and the inaccessibility of its rugged terrain. Even well-studied ranges in the Cape Fold Mountains continue to yield cryptic or previously overlooked taxa (Angus et al. 2024). Future surveys on Piketberg should target specific microhabitats rather than rely solely on generalised methods such as pitfall trapping. Two montane species not yet confirmed on Piketberg but for which suitable habitat exists are *Ouroborus cataphractus* and *Capensibufo tradouwi* (Fig. 4-A).

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